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Relationship Between Digital Entrepreneurship Skills and Business Wealth Outcomes Among Postgraduate Business Education Students in Rivers State Universities

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ABSTRACT

The study investigates relationship between digital entrepreneurship skills and business wealth outcomes among in postgraduate business education students of Rivers State Universities. Two objectives, two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted the correlation research design. The population of the study consists of one hundred and five (105) Business Education (Masters Degree) students in Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education. The entire population was used as sample for the study, since the population size was manageable. Two self-structure questionnaires titled: “Digital Entrepreneurship Skills Questionnaire (DESQ) and Wealth Creation of Business Education Postgraduate Students (WCBEPSQ). The instruments were validated by two experts in Business Education and one experts in Measurements and Evaluation. A total of 105 instruments were administered and 95 copies were retrieved and used for the study. A reliability index of 0.74 and 0.78 was achieved using Cronbach Alpha coefficient. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (r) was used to answer the research questions and multiple regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings from the study reveal that positive relationship exist between content creation, digital communication and wealth outcomes. In conclusions digital entrepreneurship skills specifically content creation, and communication skills play a significant role in wealth outcome amongst Business Education postgraduate students. Based on the findings, the following recommendation were made amongst others, that Universities should provide access to modern digital tools and laboratories for content creation to enable students to practically engage in producing marketable digital content. Stakeholders should organize seminars and training programmes on persuasive digital communication and negotiation to enable students to attract clients, retain customers, and expand their business opportunities.

Keywords: Digital Entrepreneurship, Business Wealth Outcomes, Digital Content Creation, Digital Communication Skills and Postgraduate Business Education students

INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurship education serves as a catalyst for developing digital entrepreneurial skills among Business Education students. A well-structured curriculum incorporating digital literacy, innovation management, and experiential learning can prepare students for the digital economy (Akinola, 2023). There is need for tertiary institutions of learning to provide access to digital tools, mentorship, and real-world digital business projects as this will tend to produce graduates with higher entrepreneurial intentions and capabilities (Ogunyomi & Olamide, 2023), resulting in wealth creation. Entrepreneurship

education influences students' mindset, fostering traits such as innovation, risk-taking, and opportunity recognition. The inclusion of digital skills in entrepreneurship training will enhance students' capacity to translate their ideas into viable digital ventures, thereby creating wealth (Kraus et al., 2019). This has made Entrepreneurship Education to become a key focus in the knowledge-based economy, serving as a strategic tool for fostering economic progress, stimulating innovation, and promoting wealth generation. The entrepreneur plays a pivotal role in this process by creating wealth, utilizing resources more efficiently, minimising waste, and generating employment in a challenging job market (Ejiofor & Otika, 2024). According to Ebulonu and Wordu (2025), an entrepreneur is an inventor. In the digital world, the entrepreneur is an individual who is creative and uses technology and digital skills to better the society by improving the environment through the creation of wealth for the benefit of the society. Entrepreneurship Education seeks to provide individuals with knowledge, skills, and motivation to encourage entrepreneurial success in a variety of settings. Ikpesu (2020), viewed Entrepreneurship as a way of thinking, reasoning and acting that is opportunity driven, holistic in approach and leadership balanced. Ikpesu posits that it is a dynamic process of vision, and change creation that requires the application of energy and passion towards the implementation of new ideas and creative solutions. Productive entrepreneurship is important for developing a healthy economy because it is the fundamental source of economic growth and wealth creation. Entrepreneurship education, can serve as a powerful tool that equips students with the skills and mindsets necessary for wealth creation and fostering sustainable economic growth. Entrepreneurship Education equips students with the tools to succeed. By promoting small businesses, encouraging innovation, enhancing digital skills and fostering a supportive environment, it lays a vital foundation for wealth creation, even in challenging economic conditions (Ebulonu & Wordu, 2025). One way the students could create wealth is through digital entrepreneurship skill.

Digital entrepreneurship skills refer to the capabilities required to initiate, manage, and scale entrepreneurial ventures using digital technologies (Giones & Brem, 2017). These skills include, but are not limited to, digital marketing, e-commerce operations, data analytics, content creation, digital communication skill, search engine optimisation, social media management, digital finance, and the use of entrepreneurial software applications. These skills empower entrepreneurs to identify opportunities, access broader markets, reduce costs, and enhance efficiency in delivering products or services (Le Dinh. Da Costa, & Belkhouja, 2018). The relevance of digital entrepreneurship skills has grown in tandem with the proliferation of the internet, mobile technologies, and social media platforms. According to Nambisan (2017), digital technologies redefine entrepreneurial processes by enabling new modes of innovation and business modeling, thrive in digital entrepreneurship.

Digital entrepreneurship skills according to Mhlanga (2022), are the competencies required to create, manage, and grow a business in the digital environment using technology-driven tools and platforms. These skills enable entrepreneurs to harness the power of digital technologies such as e-commerce, social media, and mobile apps, cloud computing, data analytics, and artificial intelligence to innovate, deliver value, and remain competitive in the global market. Digital entrepreneurship skills enable entrepreneurs and business owners to effectively meet customer needs by enhancing service delivery through technology. These skills involve the integration of digital tools and knowledge into the daily operations of a business, fostering efficiency, innovation, and competitiveness in the digital economy (OECD, 2023)

A study by Elia, Margherita and Passiante (2020) on European students revealed that digital skills significantly predict entrepreneurial success and revenue generation. Similarly, in a Nigerian context, Adeyemi and Olayemi (2022) found that students with training in digital marketing and e-commerce were more likely to start profitable ventures during and after their academic programmes. George and Oseni (2024) also conducted a survey of Business Education students in Rivers State and found that over 60% of digitally skilled students had monetised their knowledge through freelance, affiliate marketing, and digital content creation, contributing significantly to their income levels and economic independence.

The advancement of digital technologies has revolutionised marketing practices, making digital marketing a pivotal strategy in modern entrepreneurship. Digital marketing could be seen as the use of digital channels, tools, and platforms to promote products, services, or brands to targeted audiences. With the exponential growth of internet access, mobile devices, and social media platforms, digital marketing has

emerged as a powerful tool for wealth creation, especially among entrepreneurs, small businesses, and students in business-related disciplines (Chaffey & Ellis-Chadwick, 2019). According to Ryan (2016), digital marketing encompasses a range of strategies such as search engine optimization (SEO), content marketing, email marketing, pay-per-click (PPC) advertising, affiliate marketing, and social media marketing. It allows businesses and individuals to reach vast audiences across geographical boundaries, leveraging tools like Google Ads, Facebook Ads, Instagram, LinkedIn, YouTube, and Tik Tok. Kotler, Kartajaya and Setiawan (2021) describe digital marketing as a shift from mass marketing to personalised, data-driven engagement that creates value for both the producer and the consumer. The rise of the digital economy has brought about a significant shift in how value is created, exchanged, and monetised. Among the most impactful developments is digital content creation and digital communication skills.

Digital content creation has emerged not only as a form of expression and communication but also as a viable source of income and wealth creation (Ismail & Dada, 2022) Digital content creators often known as influencers, bloggers, or digital entrepreneurs leverage platforms like YouTube, TikTok Instagram, podcasts, and blogs to reach global audiences, engage communities, and monetise their expertise or creativity. For many young people, especially students and digital natives, content creation represents a modern pathway to entrepreneurship and financial independence (Ehulonu & Wordu, 2023). Digital content creation refers to the generation of material for digital platforms, including written, audio, and visual content aimed at educating, entertaining, or persuading audiences online (Ryan, 2016). This content is typically shared through websites, blogs, podcasts, YouTube channels, and social media. According to Chaffey and Ellis-Chadwick (2019), effective content creation is guided by audience insights, search engine optimization (SEO), platform-specific algorithms, and engagement metrics Content creation requires skills in copywriting, video editing, graphic design, and analytics Digital entrepreneurship also required skill in digital communication.

In the digital age, communication skills have evolved beyond traditional interpersonal interaction to include the ability to communicate effectively through digital platforms. Digital communication skills encompass the competencies needed to convey, interpret, and exchange information through online media, such as email, social media, video conferencing, websites, mobile apps, and collaborative tools. These skills are critical for personal branding, marketing, customer engagement, and professional networking all of which are essential to wealth creation, especially among entrepreneurs, students, and small business owners The convergence of communication and technology has made it possible for individuals to leverage digital platforms to create and exchange value, build audiences, and monetise interactions, making digital communication a strategic tool for financial success in the 21st-century knowledge economy. Digital communication skills involve the ability to use digital tools to interact effectively, efficiently, and ethically across various digital channels. These include: drafting professional emails and messages, managing social media communication, participating in video calls and webinars, creating digital presentations and multimedia content and engaging in online negotiation and collaboration (Ryan, 2016). Chaffey and Ellis-Chadwick (2019) assert that effective digital communication requires clarity, adaptability, responsiveness, and a strong understanding of digital etiquette and audience behaviour. These skills are now fundamental in Business, Education, marketing, and entrepreneurship, to enhance wealth creation /outcomes.

Wealth outcomes involves generating income, assets, and economic value through productive activities. Digital entrepreneurship offers multiple pathways to wealth outcome by lowering entry barriers, enabling access to global markets, and allowing entrepreneurs to scale rapidly with minimal physical infrastructure (Elia, Margherita, & Passiante, 2020). For business education students, acquiring digital entrepreneurial skills equips them to start ventures, generate revenue through online platforms, and build personal and communal wealth. Several studies have linked digital entrepreneurship to job creation, income generation, and economic empowerment (OECD, 2021) For instance, Adeyemi and Olayemi (2022) found that Nigerian university students who possessed strong digital entrepreneurship skills were more likely to engage in e-commerce businesses, freelance digital services, and content monetization. These activities directly contributed to their financial independence and ability to employ others. Mhlanga (2022) stated that wealth outcomes are generated through increased access to income-generating platforms, low-cost

business startups, digital innovation and value creation job and self –employment creation and financial inclusion/online banking digital financial literacy. The author stressed further that Digital entrepreneurship skills open access to global markets via platforms such as Amazon, Etsy, Instagram, TikTok, and YouTube. For example, business students who master video content creation or social media marketing can monetize these skills as influencers, freelancers, or e-commerce sellers. Low-Cost Business Startups: Unlike traditional business models, digital entrepreneurship requires minimal capital to start. Skills in web development, mobile apps, or dropshipping allow individuals to set up virtual businesses with low overhead, thereby accelerating outzone wealth outcome without the barriers of physical infrastructure. Digital Innovation and Value Creation: Digital entrepreneurship fosters innovative solutions that solve real-world problems. Skills in coding, or AI integration allow students to create products that are in demand, generating both social and financial value. Supporting the above view, Akinola (2023) submitted that, with the right digital skills, entrepreneur can create micro-enterprises and expand them to hire others, thus contributing to broader employment and wealth in their communities. The author affirmed that financial Inclusion and Online Banking Digital financial literacy including the use of fintech apps, online banking and mobile wallets improves the capacity for saving investment, and capital management, which are vital aspects of personal and business wealth growth. There is need for bossiness education student to be acquainted with those skills to enable them create wealth.

Despite the recognized importance of digital entrepreneurship, several challenges hinder Business Education students from acquiring the necessary skills. These include lack of access to digital infrastructure training facilities, limited mentorship, and low digital literacy among lecturers (Ehulonu & Word, 2025). In many developing countries, such as Nigeria, institutional and policy gaps further exacerbate these challenges, limiting students ability to fully harness digital tools for entrepreneurship. George and One, (2004) asserts that there is often a mismatch between theoretical instruction and practical skill development in many tertiary institutions, which hinders effective leaning. The lack of hands-on exposure to digital tools and platforms results in a skills gap, reducing students' readiness to participate in digital entrepreneurship

Statement of the Problem

The increasing unemployment rate among graduates in Nigeria, particularly in Rivers State, has necessitated the exploration of alternative means of livelihood. Digital entrepreneurship skills when acquired brings about wealth creation. Despite the growing emphasis on entrepreneurship education in universities, many Business Education Postgraduate students in Rivers State universities lack the digital entrepreneurship skills to harness digital opportunities such as digital content creation and digital communication skills in driving economic growth, thereby limiting their potential for wealth creation. On this note, this study aims to investigate the relationship between digital entrepreneurship skills and wealth creation among Business Education postgraduate students in Rivers State universities, with a view to identify the digital skills gaps and proposing strategies for enhancing wealth creation among these students

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to ascertain the relationship between digital entrepreneurship skills and wealth outcomes of postgraduate Business Education students in Rivers State universities. Specifically, the study sought to

1. Determine the relationship between digital content creation skills and business wealth outcome among postgraduate Business Education students in Rivers State universities
2. Determine the relationship between digital communication skills and business wealth outcome among postgraduate Business Education students in Rivers State universities

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. What is the relationship between digital skills and business wealth outcome among postgraduate Business Education students in Rivers State universities?
2. What is the relationship between digital communication skills and business wealth outcome among postgraduate Business Education students in Rivers State universities?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses formulated were tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. There is no significant relationship between digital content creation skills and business wealth outcomes among postgraduate Business Education students in Rivers State Universities
2. There is no significant relationship between digital communication skills and business wealth outcomes among postgraduate Business Education students in Rivers State Universities

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted correlational research design, to establish the relationship between digital entrepreneurship skills and wealth outcome of postgraduate business education students. The study was conducted in Rivers State, Nigeria and the main focus was on Business Education Postgraduate students (Master's Degree) in Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education (2025/2026 academic session). The population of the study consists of one hundred and five (105) Business Education Postgraduate (Master degree students) in Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education that have taking at least a course in entrepreneurship education. The entire population was used as sample for the study, since the population size was manageable. Two self-structured sets of questionnaires were used as instruments for data collection. The first instrument was to find out the Digital Entrepreneurship Skills Acquired by Business Education Postgraduate Students and second instrument was to find out Wealth Creation of Business Education Postgraduate Students. The instruments were structured on a 4 points rating scale of Strongly Agreed (SA 4-points), Agreed (A 3-Points), Disagreed (D 2-Points), and Strongly Disagreed (SD 1-point). The first instrument was titled; Digital Entrepreneurship Skills acquired by Business Education Postgraduate Students (ESBEPS) and the second instruments was titled; Wealth Creation of Business Education Postgraduate Students (WCBEPS). The instruments were validated by two experts in Business Education and one experts in Measurement and Evaluation. The reliability of the instrument was achieved by administering 20 copies of the questionnaire to Business Education postgraduate students at university of Uyo, since they are not part of the study and a reliability index of 0.74 was achieved for (ESBEPS) and 0.78 for (DWCBEPS) using Cronbach Alpha coefficient, to ascertain the internal consistency of the instruments. The instruments was were administered by the researcher personally to the respondents and was retrieved after one week. Out of the one hundred and five (105) copies of the instruments administered, only ninety-five (95) copies was retrieved and used for the analysis. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (r) was used to answer the research questions and multiple regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 levels of significance and decision was made on the r-value.

PRESENTATION OF RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What is the relationship between Digital content creation skill and wealth creation among business Education postgraduate students in Rivers State Universities?*

Table 1: Respondent Rating of Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient on the Relationship between Digital Content Creation and Business Wealth Outcome Among Postgraduate Business Education Students.

		Content Creation	Wealth outcome
Content creation	Pearson Correlation sig.	1	0.54
	(2-tailed)		0.00
	N	95	95
Wealth Outcome	Pearson Correlation sig.	0.54	1
	(2-tailed)	0.00	
	N	95	95

Source: Researcher's Field Survey (2026).

The analysis from Table1 indicates a calculated coefficient (1) value based on the response of Business Education postgraduate student, establishing the relationship between digital content creation skills and

business wealth outcome among Business Education postgraduate students in Rivers State universities. The table shows a calculated r value of 0.54, this means that there is a moderate positive relationship between digital content creation skills and business wealth outcome among Business Education postgraduate students. Therefore, an increase in digital content creation skills leads to increase in wealth creation.

Research Question 2: *What is the relationship between digital communication skills and business wealth outcome among postgraduate Business Education students in Rivers State universities?*

Table 2: Respondent Rating of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient on the Relationship between Digital Communication Skills and Business Wealth Outcomes Among Postgraduate Business Education Student

		Digital Communication	Wealth outcome
Digital Communication skills	Pearson Correlation	1	0.54
	sig. (2-tailed)		0.00
	N	95	95
			1
Wealth Outcome	Pearson Correlation	0.98	
	sig. (2-tailed)	0.00	
	N	95	95

Source: Researcher’s Field Survey (2026).

The analysis from Table 2 indicates a calculated coefficient (1) value based on the responses from Business Education postgraduate students, establishing the relationship between digital communication skills and business wealth creation among Business Education postgraduate students in Rivers State universities. The table shows a calculated r value of 0.98, this means that there is a very strong positive relationship between digital communication skills and business wealth creation among Business Education postgraduate students. Therefore, an increase in digital communication skills leads to increase in wealth creation.

Table 3: Model summary of Regression Analysis of Digital Entrepreneurship Skills and Business Wealth Outcomes

Mode	R	R square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change R Square Change	Statistics F Change	Df1	Df2	Sig. F change
1	.084a	0.07	-.026	.17731	0.07	.198	3	91	.898

a. Predictors (Constant), digital communication and content creation

b. Dependent variable: Wealth outcome

Source: Researcher’s Field Survey (2026).

Table 3: shows coefficient of determination (R square) 0.07 which mean 7 percent variation in dependent variable (wealth outcomes) is explained by independent variable (digital communication content creation) goodness of fit regression model.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between digital content creation skills and business wealth outcome among postgraduate Business Education students in Rivers State Universities.

Regression coefficient table of relationship between digital content creation skill and business wealth outcome among postgraduate business education student in rivers state universities

The regression coefficient of digital content creation skills on business wealth outcomes is found to be 0.54 which implies that any students who engages in digital content creation could easily create wealth

Model	Unstandardized coefficients B	Standardized Coefficients Beta	T	sig
1 (Constant)	3.06		14.38	0.00
Content Creation	0.55	-.062	-769	.000

for himself and others. Also the regression coefficient is significant as p-value (0.00) is less than level of significance level (0.05). thus the hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, there is significant relationship

between digital content creations skills and wealth outcomes of postgraduate Business Education students in Rivers State University.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significance relationship between Digital Communication Skill and Business Wealth Outcome Among Postgraduate Business Education Students in Rivers State Universities.

Table 4: Regression Coefficient Table of Relationship Between Digital Communication Skills and Business Wealth Outcomes of Postgraduate Business Education Students in Rivers State Universities.

Model	Unstandardized coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	sig
	B	Std Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	3.06	0.21		14.38	0.00
Digital Communication	0.33	0.07	0.34	.462s	.000

Source: Researcher’s Field Survey (2026).

The regression coefficient of digital communication skills on business wealth outcome is found to be 0.33 which implies that any students who engages in digital communication could easily create wealth for himself and other. Also, the regression coefficient is significant as p-value (0.00) is less than level of significance (0.05). Thus the hypothesis was rejected. therefore, there is significant relationship between digital communication skills and wealth creation of postgraduate Business Education students in Rivers State Universities.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The discussion was done according to each findings in the research question;

Relationship between Digital Content Creation Skills and business Wealth Outcomes Postgraduate among Business Education Students

The analysis from research question one reveals a statistically significant relationship between digital content creation skills and wealth outcomes among Business Education postgraduate students in Rivers State universities. The calculated Pearson correlation coefficient (r) of 0.54 indicates a moderate strong positive correlation, suggesting that students who possess higher digital content creation skills are more likely to engage in wealth-generating activities. This finding is further supported by the regression analysis, which shows a regression coefficient of 0.55. This implies that for every unit increase in digital content creation skills, there is a corresponding 0.55 unit increase in business wealth outcome. In practical terms, postgraduate students who develop digital content creation competencies such as creating blogs, videos, podcasts, or social media content can leverage these skills to generate income, build personal brands, and create entrepreneurial opportunities. Moreover, the p-value of 0.00, which is lower than the significance threshold of 0.05, indicates that the regression coefficient is statistically significant. This means the observed relationship is not due to chance. As such, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between digital content creation skills and business wealth creation is rejected. This study is in line with the view of Ismail and Dada (2022) that digital content creation, which involves the production and distribution of digital media such as videos, blogs, podcasts, graphics, and social media posts for online consumption

In the researcher's viewpoint, digital content creation skills represent a vital instrument for Business Education students in their pursuit of business wealth creation. The contemporary business environment thrives on creativity and the ability to communicate value effectively through diverse digital platforms. Digital content creation is not merely a tool for communication but a driver of economic empowerment

Relationship between Digital Communication Skills and Business Wealth Outcomes Postgraduate Among Business Education Postgraduate Students

The findings from research question 2 provide clear evidence of a significant relationship between digital communication skills and wealth outcomes among Business Education postgraduate students in Rivers State universities. The calculated Pearson correlation coefficient (r) of 0.98 indicates a very strong positive correlation. This high value suggests that improvements in digital communications skills are

closely associated with increased capacity for wealth creation among the students. Further analysis through regression shows a coefficient of 0.33, which implies that for every unit increase in digital communication skills, there is a corresponding 0.33 unit increase in wealth creation. This indicates that digital communication skills, though slightly less impactful than other digital skill areas examined, still play a meaningful role in enabling students to engage with potential customers, collaborate effectively, promote their services, and manage digital business interactions. The significance of this relationship is statistically confirmed by a p-value of 0.00 which is below the 0.05 level of significance. This means the relationship observed is not due to random chance, and therefore, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between digital communication skills and wealth creation is rejected. This is in line with the view of Ryan (2016) that digital communication skills involve the ability to use digital tools to interact effectively, efficiently, and ethically across various digital channels. These include crafting professional emails and messages, managing social media communication, participating in video calls and webinars, creating digital presentations and multimedia content and engaging in online negotiation and collaboration.

In the researchers' viewpoint, digital communication skills are indispensable for Business Education students in achieving business wealth creation in today's interconnected world. Effective communication is at the heart of every successful business, and in the digital era, the ability to convey ideas, negotiate, and maintain professional relationships through online platforms are critical assets.

CONCLUSION

This study has established that digital entrepreneurship skills, specifically content creation, and communication skills play a significant role in business wealth outcome among Business Education postgraduate students in Rivers State universities. The strong positive relationships show statistically significant results from the analyses indicating that students who possess and effectively apply these digital skills are better positioned to explore entrepreneurial opportunities, generate income, and contribute to economic development. In today's digital-driven economy, equipping postgraduate students with relevant digital competencies is essential for fostering innovation, self-employment, and financial empowerment. Therefore, enhancing digital entrepreneurship education through curriculum development, practical training, and industry collaboration is vital to preparing Business Education students for sustainable wealth creation in the 21st century.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were made based on the findings:

1. Universities should provide access to modern digital tools and laboratories for content creation to enable students to practically engage in producing marketable digital content.
2. Stakeholders should organize seminars and training programmes on persuasive digital communication and negotiation to enable students to attract clients, retain customers, and expand their business opportunities.

REFERENCES

- Adeyemi, A. O. & Ojayemi, B. M. (2022). Digital entrepreneurship skills and income generation among university students in Nigeria. *Journal of Digital Innovation and Entrepreneurship*, 4(2), 112-129.
- Akinola, O. A. (2023). Bridging the gap between education and practice: Integrating digital entrepreneurship in Nigerian universities. *International Journal of Business and Education Research*, 5(1), 21-34.
- Chaffey, D., & Ellis-Chadwick, F. (2019). *Digital marketing* (7th ed.). Harlow, UK: Pearson Education.
- Ehulonu, G., & Wordu, J. A. (2025). Digital skills and entrepreneurship education: Pathways to wealth creation in a depressed economy. *UAI Journal of Economics, Business and Management (UALJEBM)*, 1(1), 5-11

- Ejiofor, U. H., & Otuka, U. S. (2024). The anatomy of Igbo apprenticeship system: The entrepreneurship perspective. *Journal of Business and Economic Research*, 10(1), 87-97
- Elia, G., Margherita, A., & Passionate, G. (2020). Digital entrepreneurship ecosystem: How digital technologies foster entrepreneurial dynamics. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 150, 119791.
- George, T., & Oseni, A. O. (2024). Entrepreneurial digital skills and economic empowerment of business education students in Nigerian universities. *Nigerian Journal of Business Education*, 9(1), 33-48.
- Giones, F., & Brem, A. (2017). Digital technology entrepreneurship: A definition and research agenda. *Technology Innovation Management Review*, 7(5), 44-51.
- Godpower, Y. J., & Egbunefu, C. (2024). Relationship between digital entrepreneurship skills and wealth creation among postgraduate business education students in Rivers State universities. *Rivers State University Journal of Education*, 27(1), 171-178.
- Ikpesu, O.C. (2020). *Fundamentals of Entrepreneurship Practice*. Divine stone Publication, Lagos
- Ismail, B. A., & Dada, A. A. (2022). Digital marketing and youth entrepreneurship: Evidence from Nigeria's online economy. *Journal of Marketing and Digital Innovation*, 3(2), 89-105.
- Kotler, P., Kartajaya, H., & Setiawan, I. (2021) *Marketing 5.0: Technology for humanity*. Hoboken, NJ: Wiley,
- Kraus, S. Palmer, C., Kailer, N. Kallinger, F. L. & Spitzer, J. (2019). Digital entrepreneurship A research agenda on new business models for the twenty-first century. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research*, 25(2), 353-375
- Le Dinh, T. Da Costa, G., & Belkhouja, M. (2018) Digital entrepreneurship: An exploratory study. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research*, 24(2), 278-298
- Mhlanga, D. (2022) Digital transformation and the future of African small and medium enterprises. *Technology in Society* 70, 101993.
- Nambisan, S. (2017) Digital entrepreneurship Toward a digital technology perspective of entrepreneurship. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 41(6), 1029-1055
- OECD (2023) *The digital transformation of SMEs*. OECD Publishing <https://doi.org/10.1787/1f2da30b-en>
- Ogunyomi, PO., & Olamide, J. A (2023) Enhancing business students' digital competence through entrepreneurship education. *Journal of Educational Innovation and Technology*. 11(4), 76-89
- Ryan, D. (2016). *Understanding digital marketing Marketing strategies for engaging the digital generation* (4th ed) London Kogan Page.
- Tiago, MTPM B., & Verissimo, J. M. C. (2014) Digital marketing and social media. Why bother? *Business Horizons*. 57(6), 703-708
- World Economic Forum (2023). *Future of jobs report 2023*. Geneva: World Economic Forum.